

Determination of Trans-Fatty Acid Levels in Selected Syrian Food Products

تحديد مستويات الأحماض الدهنية المتحولة في بعض المنتجات الغذائية السورية

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Submitted date: 30 October 2024 - Accepted date: 5 January 2025

ABSTRACT

Trans fatty acid (TFA) consumption correlates with negative health effects and contributes significantly to morbidity and mortality worldwide. The current study aimed to determine the levels of trans fatty acids (TFAs) and conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) in some Syrian food products to develop a TFAs composition database that would provide authorities with information on TFAs levels in Syrian food. In 2022, eighty-three samples were collected from Damascus city's local market, including cow's ghee (n=9), palm oil (n=7), sardine (n=9), olive oil (n=30, some of them are bottled in glass or plastic bottles and the others from local olive presses), soybean oil (n=7), sunflower oil (n=7), flaxseed oil (n=5), and sesame oil (n=2). The Soxhlet method was used to extract the lipids from the samples (except oils), then the methyl esters of fatty acids (FAME) were prepared and the concentration of fatty acids (g/100g) was determined using gas chromatography (GC) equipped with a Split/Splitless injector and a flame ionization detector (FID). The results revealed that the levels of Trans fatty acids (TFAs) ranged in all samples from 0.04 to 1.82 g/100g, with high amounts (4.78%) found in one sample of cow's ghee, two samples of palm oil, and one sample of soybean oil. The olive oil, Flaxseed oil, sesame oil, and sardine contained less than 1 g TFAs/100g. Compared with the other samples, cow's ghee showed the highest CLA concentration (0.60 g/100g). These findings suggest that additional reductions in Syria are required to properly meet public health objectives and lower the incidence of illnesses such as coronary heart disease.

Keywords: Trans Fatty Acids, Conjugated Linoleic Acid, Gas Chromatography, Syria.

المخلص

يرتبط استهلاك الأحماض الدهنية المتحولة (TFAs) بالتأثيرات الصحية السلبية في صحة الإنسان، ويسهم على نحو كبير في زيادة معدلات الأمراض والوفيات في جميع أنحاء العالم. هدف البحث إلى تحديد مستويات TFAs وحمض اللينوليك المترافق (CLA) في بعض المنتجات الغذائية السورية لتطوير قاعدة بيانات عن TFAs، التي من شأنها أن تقدم معلومات عن مستوياتها في الغذاء السوري للجهات الحكومية. جُمعت ٧٦ عينة غذائية مختلفة خلال عام ٢٠٢٢ من السوق المحلية لمدينة دمشق وشملت: السمن الحيواني البقري (٩ عينات)، زيت النخيل (٧ عينات)، السردين المجد (٩ عينات)، زيت الزيتون البكر (٣٠ عينة، بعضها معبأ في عبوات زجاجية أو بلاستيكية وبعضها الآخر من معاصر الزيتون)، زيت فول الصويا (٧ عينات)، زيت عباد الشمس (٧ عينات)، زيت بذور الكتان (٥ عينات)، زيت السمسم (عينتان). بدايةً، استخلص الدهن من العينات باستعمال جهاز سوكسليت، ثم حُضر ميثيل استر الأحماض الدهنية (FAME)، وقُدر تركيز الأحماض الدهنية (غ/١٠٠) باستخدام الكروماتوغرافيا الغازية (GC) المزود بنظام حقن Split/Splitless وكاشف اللهب المتأين (FID). أظهرت النتائج أن مستويات الأحماض الدهنية المفروقة (ترانس) تراوحت بين ٠,٠٤ و ١,٨٢ غ/١٠٠ غ في جميع العينات المدروسة، مع وجود تراكيز عالية (< ٢٪) في عينة واحدة من السمن الحيواني، وعينتين من زيت النخيل، وعينة واحدة من زيت فول الصويا. احتوى زيت الزيتون وزيت بذور الكتان وزيت السمسم والسردين على أقل من ١ غ TFAs / ١٠٠ غ. مقارنةً مع العينات الأخرى، أظهر السمن الحيواني أعلى تركيز من حمض اللينوليك المترافق (CLA) (٠,٦٠ غ / ١٠٠ غ). تشير هذه النتائج إلى وجود حاجة إلى خفض مستويات TFA في سورية لتلبية أهداف الصحة العامة وتقليل حدوث الأمراض كأمراض القلب التاجية. **الكلمات المفتاحية:** الأحماض الدهنية المفروقة، حمض اللينوليك المترافق، الكروماتوغرافيا الغازية، سورية.

INTRODUCTION

Trans fatty acids (TFAs) are unsaturated fatty acids with at least one double bond that is in the trans configuration. TFA are primarily derived from two sources: (1) ruminant trans fats, which occur naturally in dairy products and meat from ruminant animals; and (2) industrial trans fats, which are generated through the partial hydrogenation of vegetable oils [1]. During the thermal preparation

of food, such as frying and baking, small amounts of TFA are also produced[2]. Trans isomers of oleic acid (18:1) are the most common in food products, followed by trans isomers of linoleic acid (18:2 n6), linolenic acid (18:3 n3), and palmitoleic acid (16:1). Cow's ghee and partially hydrogenated fats have significantly different amounts and qualities of TFA [3]. Conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) is a polyunsaturated

fatty acid present in animal fats such as red meat and dairy products [4]. Minimal amounts of CLA are present naturally in plant lipids, and various CLA isomers are generated via the chemical hydrogenation of fats (as illustrated in Figure 1). However, the CLA is not labeled as trans-fats [5]. Over the last three decades, there has been a growing amount of convincing scientific research on the health-damaging consequences of TFA [6]. TFA consumption has been linked to an increased risk of heart disease. TFA may increase the concentration of low-density lipoprotein (LDL) cholesterol while decreasing the concentration of high-density lipoprotein (HDL) cholesterol, both of which are risk factors for coronary heart disease [7]. According to the World Health Organization, TFA consumption should not exceed 1% of total daily energy intake (equal to less than 2.2 g/day in a 2000-calorie diet) [8]. The amount of trans fats in various food products and their daily intake in many countries has been estimated. TFA levels (g/100 g food) ranged from 0 to 0.246 in Argentina [9] and from 0 to 22.96 in India [10]. Ismail et al. [11] evaluated TFA in traditional and commonly consumed Egyptian foods and found that 34% of the products exceeded the TFA limit. Many Countries like Denmark, the United States, and Canada, have begun to reduce and eliminate trans fats in food through legislative initiatives that involved the implementation of regulations setting maximum limits of trans fats or mandated labeling of trans fats [12]. The United Arab Emirates is one of the leading Arab countries that have banned the presence of TFA in food products [13]. To our knowledge, no data on the trans fatty acids (TFAs) content of Syrian foods are available. Therefore, the current work's objective is to give accurate and up-to-date information on the TFAs content of food products sold in Syria to create a steppingstone for the necessary laws and regulations to impose restrictions on the concentration of TFAs in imported or locally produced foods.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Chemicals

TFA Standards, Hexan, Methanol, Sodium sulfate, Benzene, and Boron trifluoride were obtained from Merck (Germany). Fatty acids standard, namely: Methyl trans-9-Octadecenoate (elaidic acid methyl ester), Trans-11-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester (trans vaccenic acid methyl ester), Methyl cis-9-hexadecenoate (oleic acid methyl ester), linoleic acid methyl ester mix cis/trans, linolenic acid methyl ester isomer mix cis/trans, were purchased from Sigma-Aldrich (Germany).

Food samples

Seventy-six samples were collected from the local market of Damascus city in 2022. The samples included: Cow's ghee (n=9), palm oil (n=7), Sardine (n=9), Olive oil (n=30), Soybean oil (n=7), Sunflower Oil (n=7), Flaxseed oil (n=5), and Sesame Oil (n=2)

Extraction of Fat

The Soxhlet method was used to extract the lipids from the samples (except oils) according to the method of AOAC (2019) [14]; briefly, 10 g of the sample were put into extraction thimble, which were extracted using 250 mL of N-Hexane, for 8 h. The extracted fat was used to prepare the methyl esters of fatty acids. The fats' percentage in sardine samples were determined according to the Soxhlet method, but the fat which used in the preparation of FAME was extracted using a novel "cold method", briefly, 10 g of the sardine sample was freeze-dried for 8 h. then the freeze-dried material was crushed manually using a porcelain pistol and mortar, transferred into airtight-screw cap glass bottle, soaked in 20 mL of N-Hexane, put in fridge (4°C) for 24 h. The N-Hexane (which containing the fat) was filtered, evaporated with Nitrogen current, and finely used to prepare FAMES as described above. This novel method protected the polyunsaturated fatty acids (PUFAs), specially EPA and DHA from decomposition.

Fatty acids methyl esters preparation

The methyl esters of fatty acids (FAME) were prepared according to the procedure described by Morrison and Smith [15]. In a test tube, 0.02 g of fat was mixed with 2 ml of high-purity benzene and 2 ml of 7% BF₃ in methanol. The tube's vertical space was filled with nitrogen, closed tightly, and incubated in a boiling water bath (Memmert wb 14 models) for 60 minutes. After the mixture was cooled, 2 ml of n-hexane and 2 ml of water were added, and the tubes were centrifuged at 2000 rpm for 5 min. The supernatant was collected, transferred to a clean tube, mixed with 2 ml of water, and centrifuged again. The hexane layer was separated and mixed with anhydrous sodium sulphate, and 1μl was taken and injected into a gas chromatograph.

GC condition

TFA was determined using a gas chromatograph (Shimadzu 17A, Japan) equipped with a Split/Splitless injector and a flame ionization detector (FID). A capillary column, PRECIX HP 2340 (60 m x 0.25 mm x 0.20 m film thickness), was used to separate and quantify each FAME component. The oven temperature program was set at 175 oC for 18 minutes, then the temperature was increased to 190oC at 5°C per minute, and the final temperature (190 oC) was maintained for 12 minutes. Nitrogen was used

as the carrier gas at a flow rate of 1 mL/min. Methyl trans-9-Octadecenoate (elaidic acid methyl ester), Trans-11-Octadecenoic acid methyl ester (trans vaccenic acid methyl ester), Methyl cis-9-hexadecenoate (oleic acid methyl ester), linoleic acid methyl ester mix cis/trans (including CLAs, linoleic

acid and trans linoleic acid), linolenic acid methyl ester isomer mix cis/trans, were identified (as shown in figure 1). The quantitative determination of trans fatty acid was calculated according to the peak areas.

Figure 1. linoleic acid and conjugated linoleic acid (CLA) formulae: (A) linoleic acid, (B) and (C) conjugated linoleic acids

Figure 1. Fatty acid methyl esters (FAMES) standard mixture

RESULTS

TFAs in cow's ghee

The results in Table 1 showed that the total TFA in cow's ghee ranged from 0.63 to 4.78 g/100 g. The results also showed that vaccenic acid was the major trans-18:1 isomer in the samples. Also, CLA with a concentration ranging from 0.21 to 1.35% was detected in cow's ghee samples (Table 1).

TFAs in Olive Oil

The trans fatty acid content of the olive oil samples investigated is shown in Table 2 and varied between 0.0103 and 0.3349 g/100 g oil.

TFAs in Soybean, Sunflower, Flaxseed, and Sesame oils

The Trans fatty acids content in soybean oil varied between 0.042 and 2.32 g/100g (Table 3). Table 3 shows the overall percentages (%) of TFA isomers detected in the sunflower oil samples tested. The TFA concentrations in the samples ranged from 0.13 to 1.23 g/100g. Table 3 also shows the distribution of TFAs in commercial flaxseed oil samples. The most common TFA isomers found in flaxseed oils were C18:3, followed by C18:2. While C18:1 trans-9, C18:1 trans-11, and CLA were not detected (as shown in Figure 3). Table 3 illustrates the percentage of TFA in two examined sesame oil samples. The TFA concentrations observed in sesame oil ranged between 0.06 and 0.35 g/100 g (as shown in Figure 4)

TFAs in Palm Oil

Table 4 presents the TFA in palm oil samples. The average total TFA in seven samples of palm oil was 0.65%, with a range of 0.06 to 2.62%. Of the seven commercial palm oil samples, one sample was found to contain a high level of TFA (2.6264 g/100 g).

TFAs in Sardine

TFA levels in sardine samples ranged from 0.087 to 0.75% (Table 5).

DISCUSSION

Cow's ghee contains about 2.7% TFA with one or more trans-double bonds. Our results for TFAs in milk are consistent with the findings of Precht and Molken-entin [16] and Vargas-Bello Pérez and Garnsworthy [17]. According to Shingfield et al [18], the trans-11 isomer is the main trans fatty acid in the group of trans-C18:1 isomers in cow's ghee and represents about 40–50% of the total C18:1 trans fatty acids. Natural TFA, like vaccenic acid (18:1 t11), has anti-atherosclerotic and anti-diabetic properties [19]. The difference in vaccenic acid concentration between the samples investigated could be attributed to differences in the animal feeding system, which affects the amount of this isomer in cow's ghee [20]. Dairy products contain the natural trans fatty acid

conjugated linoleic acid (CLA), which has been linked to a lower risk of heart disease [21]. Vargas and Garnsworthy [17] confirmed that rumen bacteria can biohydrogenation unsaturated fatty acids and produce CLA. The variation in CLA concentration between samples is due to the difference in predominant microbial species and the diet offered to the animal [22]. All the olive oil samples studied were within the Syrian National Standard specification of olive oil (C18:1 T \leq 0.05) [23], except for two samples for a total of C18:2 T + C18:3 T. This study's results agree with the findings of Sakar et al. [24], who found that the trans fatty acid level of Moroccan olive oil was between 0.09 and 0.04 g/100 g fat. The total TFA content of Costa Rican and Egyptian olive oil samples is around 0.23 and 0.4 g/100 g, respectively [25] [11]. The amount of trans fatty acids in the Syrian olive oil samples varied, which may be related to differences in olive types, geographic area, and extraction methods. Sakar et al. [24] found a high level of TFA value in the super-pressure system, while the lowest one was displayed by the traditionally extracted oil, and the TFA correlated positively to K232, K270, and acid values. Our data revealed that the mean levels of TFA in soybean oil (1.0056%) were lower than the TFA concentration in Malaysian soybean oil (5.79%) [26]. The most frequent TFA in the soybean oil samples were C18:2 trans, C18:3 trans, and C18:1 trans-9. Soybean oil often contains more C18:2 trans isomers than C18:1 trans fatty acids, according to Aro et al. [27]. TFA in sunflower oils is probably generated by heating sunflower seeds before or during the extraction process [28]. Hou et al. [7] examined 22 samples of sunflower oil and found that the mean TFA was 1.41%, while Hoteit et al. [29] found a low concentration of TFA in sunflower oil samples (<0.1%) collected from the Lebanese market. C18:3 and C18:2 were the most common TFA isomers in flaxseed oils, which could be attributed to the lower levels of oleic and linoleic acids in linseed oil, which have been shown to be more stable than linolenic acid [30]. Bezelgues and Destail- lats [31] reported that commercial linseed oil for human consumption is refined; during the refining process, TFA forms due to high amounts of unsaturated fatty acids (UFA) and high temperatures, particularly during the deodorization step. According to Johnson et al. (2009) [32], the total TFA content in Indian sesame oil was 1.3%, and Elaidic acid comprised the majority. Sesame oil's TFA in the Malaysian market ranged from 0.1 to 0.76%. While Song et al. (2015) [33] did not detect any TFA in Korean sesame oil. The presence of TFA in refined palm oils is due to thermal isomerization caused by the relatively high

temperatures of up to 260°C used during deodorization [34]. According to Hishamuddin et al. [6], TFA levels in Malaysian palm oil range between 0.24 and 0.67 g/100g. Wolff [35] has previously demonstrated that TFA formation is strongly influenced by heating time and deodorization temperature; thus, longer deodorization times at higher temperatures may increase the TFA content of refined oils. TFA was also detected at low levels in frozen sardine samples (Table 5). Nasopoulou et al. [36] found the levels of C18:1 trans (ω -9) in raw, grilled, and brined sardines to be 39.7, 65.3, and 96.7 mg/kg fish tissue, respectively.

CONCLUSIONS

The study's findings indicated that TFA of natural origin (Vaccenic acid) could be differentiated from TFA of industrial origin (Elaidic acid) in the products analyzed. We found that cow's ghee contained the highest percentages of CLA, which is known to have health advantages. Olive, sesame, and flaxseed oils are healthy oils that have low levels of TFA. Future studies will focus on the levels of TFA in other food products, especially chocolate bakery products, fast food consumed, and foods common in the Syrian local market.

Figure 3. FAMES composition of flaxseed oil (sample 1)

Table 1. Levels of TFA in cow's ghee (g/100g)

Sample	<u>Elaidic acid (C18:1 trans-9)</u>	<u>Trans vaccenic acid (C18:1 trans-11)</u>	<u>Conjugated linoleic acid (CLA)</u>	<u>Trans linoleic acid (C18:2 trans)</u>	<u>Trans linolenic acid (C18:3 trans)</u>	Total TFA per 100 g of Total Fat
1	0.15	2.09	1.06	0.45	0.27	2.96
2	ND	0.53	0.49	ND	0.10	0.63
3	0.17	0.67	0.21	ND	ND	0.84
4	0.24	0.69	0.33	0.0060	ND	0.94
5	0.32	1.56	0.42	ND	0.10	1.98
6	0.170	0.99	0.53	ND	0.16	1.32
7	0.30	1.04	0.41	0.07	0.35	1.76
8	0.93	3.51	1.35	0.31	0.03	4.78
9	0.23	0.95	0.65	ND	ND	1.18
The mean	0.27	1.34	0.60	0.09	0.11	1.82±1.32

ND: not detected.

Table (2): levels of TFAs in olive oil (g/100g)

Sample	C18:1 trans-9	C18:1 trans-11	CLA	C18:2 trans	C18:3 trans	Total TFAs per 100 g of Fat	
1	0.0068	ND	0.0184	ND	0.0287	0.0355	
2	0.0114		0.0171		0.0338		
3	0.0086		0.0184		0.0525		
4	0		0.0125		0.048		
5	0.0045		0.0132		0.032		
6	0		0.0098		0.0214		
7	0.0010		0.0127		0.0212		
8	0.0008		0.0119		0.0243		
9	ND		0.0350		0.0582		
10	ND		0.0575		0.0217		
11	ND		ND		ND		
12	ND		0.0370		0.0395		
13	0.0015		0.0182		0.0225	0.024	
14	0.0042	0.0082	0.3307	ND	0.3349		
15	ND	ND	0.0114	ND	0.0280	0.028	
16	ND		0.0115		0.0288		
17	ND		0.0134		0.0253		
18	ND		0.0131		0.0244		
19	ND		0.0132		ND	ND	
20	0.0075		0.0326		0.0086	0.0161	
21	0.0016		0.0315		ND	0.0142	0.0158
22	0.0038		0.0179			0.0065	0.0103
23	0.0033		0.0386			0.0491	0.0524
24	0.0095		ND		0.0255	0.035	
25	0.0010		0.0329		0.0300	0.031	
26	0.0021		0.0479		0.0632	0.0653	
27	0.0113	0.0108	0	0.0113			
28	0.0173	0.1297	0.1494	0.0227	0.1894		
29	0.0116	0.0330	ND	0.0389	0.0505		
30	0.0035	0.0039		0.0032	0.0067		
The mean	0.00371	ND	0.0237	0.0160	0.0249	0.0446±0.06	

ND: not detected.

Table (3): levels of TFAs in soybean, sunflower, and flaxseed oils (g/100g)						
Soybean oil						
Sample	C18:1 trans-9	C18:1 trans-11	CLA	C18:2 trans	C18:3 trans	Total TFAs per 100 g of Fat
1	0.02	ND	0.69	0.39	1.91	2.32
2	ND		ND	0.042	ND	0.042
3	ND		ND	0.14	0.78	0.92
4	0.02		ND	0.13	0.49	0.64
5	0.08		0.05	0.24	0.57	0.89
6	ND		ND	0.26	1.08	1.34
7	ND		ND	0.06	0.81	0.87
Mean	0.02		0.11	0.18	0.81	1.003±0.7
Sunflower oil						
1	ND	ND	ND	0.11	0.14	0.25
2	ND	ND	ND	0.16	0.04	0.2
3	ND	ND	ND	0.18	0.03	0.21
4	ND	ND	ND	0.23	1.00	1.23
5	0.02	ND	0.03	0.21	0.08	0.31
6	0.009	ND	0.10	0.07	0.05	0.13
7	0.019	0.07	0.17	0.11	0.072	0.27
Mean	0.007	0.01	0.04	0.15	0.20	0.371±0.38
Flaxseed oil						
1	ND	ND	ND	0.03	0.17	0.2
2				0.02	0.11	0.13
3				0.03	0.17	0.2
4				0.04	0.18	0.22
5				0.04	0.19	0.23
Mean				0.03	0.16	0.20±0.04
ND: not detected.						

Table (4): levels of TFAs in palm oil (g/100g)						
Sample	C18:1 trans-9	C18:1 trans-11	CLA	C18:2 trans	C18:3 trans	Total TFAs per 100 g of Total Fat
1	0.02	ND	0.05	0.03	0.15	0.20
2	ND	ND	0.24	ND	0.06	0.06
3	0.03	0.03	0.96	0.33	2.23	2.62
4	0.09	ND	0.65	0.02	1.02	1.13
5	ND	ND	ND	0.13	0.03	0.16
6	0.009	ND	0.100	0.07	0.046	0.13
7	0.019	0.07	0.17	0.11	0.07	0.27
The mean	0.024	0.01	0.31	0.098	0.52	0.65±1.01
ND: not detected.						

Table (5): levels of TFAs in Sardine (g/100 g)

Sample	C18:1 trans-9	C18:1 trans-11	CLA	C18:2 trans	C18:3 trans	Total TFAs per 100 g of Total Fat
1	ND	ND	0.01	0.27	0.04	0.31
2	0.04	ND	ND	0.09	ND	0.13
3	0.39	ND	ND	0.19	0.07	0.65
4	0.04	0.02	ND	ND	0.06	0.12
5	ND	ND	0.02	ND	0.07	0.087
6	ND	ND	ND	0.05	0.04	0.09
7	ND	ND	ND	0.30	0.06	0.36
8	0.26	ND	0.15	ND	0.60	0.86
9	0.04	ND	0.05	ND	0.08	0.12
The mean	0.086	0.002	0.026	0.10	0.11	0.30±0.21

ND: not detected.

Figure 3. FAMES composition of sesame oil (sample 1)

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Competing Interest: The authors declare there is no competing interest.

Fund: No Fund.

Author contributions: All authors contributed equally.

Compliance with Ethical Standards: This article does not contain any studies involving human or animal subjects.

Data and materials availability: All data and materials are available in the main text.

